

PERFECT HUMAN INTERPRETATION IN JALALIDDIN RUMI'S CREATION

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Annotation: This article highlights the educational aspects of the wisdom of Maulana Jalaluddin Rumi. In particular, the important places of Rumi's works in the spiritual world of a perfect human are revealed.

Key words: Masnavi, hikmat, "Inchingdagi inchingdatur", poetry, creation, Sufism, Sufi.

The idea of a perfect person is a spiritual and moral factor that has led not only individuals, but also entire nations to high development, and inspired them to unparalleled achievements in the field of spirituality and enlightenment. Among other scholars, Mavlana Rumi's idea of a perfect human being has been one of the central issues of our nation's ideal and mystical philosophy for several centuries. Because it was nourished by the ideas of Islam and acquired a wider meaning. High ideas about a perfect person are deeply expressed in all the works of Maulana Rumi. Maulana Rumi understood that a perfect person is kind, just, right-spoken, conscientious, honorable, strong-willed, enterprising, tenacious, self-sacrificing, high-spirited, and, in our opinion, a perfect person viewed as the bottom line and the cream of the crop. Man by nature strives for freedom and goodness. In fact, the meaning of life is living with moral values. As a result of educational and cultural teachings, Rumi's ideal of a perfect person and its criteria have been formed and developed in accordance with the spirit of the time. At the same time, it should be noted that Rumi's tolerance and moral teachings emerged as liberating ideas, as opposed to mutual wars that bring hardships to mankind.

It is the research of the significance of Maulana Rumi's theoretical and moral views on the perfect man that is becoming more and more important now. The reason is that Rumi focuses on the enrichment of the spiritual world of a person and the need to ensure the priority of morality on this basis. Philosophical solutions to problems such as self-awareness, knowing the truth, and thus achieving treatment of the heart are given on the basis of such ideas. That's why Jalaluddin Rumi said, "Man is a great miracle and everything is written inside him. But there is darkness and curtains that do not allow reading the writings. *"Darkness and veils, various activities are the actions of a person regarding worldly affairs and the endless dreams of the heart,"* he says.

Rumi's mystical teachings are based on a number of religious and educational ideas that promote universal ideals such as justice, truth, correctness, kindness, honesty, faith, hard work, and patriotism. Such ideas have passed the tests of time and serve as a foundation for the formation of the ideological foundations of a fair moral and ethical system in human-society-state relations. The immortality of Rumi's ideas about the perfect man is determined by his understanding of the essence of this idea. That's why Hazrat Maulana Rumi said in his time, "Aliymanu shavqan wa zavqan wa ana gharqa fiha", i.e., *"There was excitement and pleasure necessary for the rays of truth and faith,"* so I immersed myself in them. they said. The conclusion that can be drawn from these words of Allama is that a person finds comfort only when he reaches his level of perfection. At the same time, other people of Sufism also believed that the Supreme Truth is perfect - it strives to reach the essence of essences, which formed the basis of their thoughts. About this, Jalaluddin Rumi expresses his thoughts saying, *"Though the paths are different, but the goal is the same,"* and *"I am one with seventy-three sects."* However, some Islamic scholars accuse Rumi of disbelief. Human thinking, which has changed the times, cannot stop the struggle between sects and currents, no matter how many centuries have passed. The true essence and content of the Sufism philosophy is that no matter what historical period, what socio-political system a person lives in, first of all, he should become a perfect, mature person. A perfect person's goals are noble, they serve the betterment of society, and their activities are oriented towards goodness.

It is known that Rumi's idea of a perfect human being is considered the ideal of divine and mystical ideas in the world of Turkish and Persian literature for several centuries, which is in accordance with Sharia and Tariqat rulings. Rumi's idea of a perfect person is, firstly, the product of his natural pleasure from the mysteries of the divine world, and his desire for it, and secondly, the need to create practical guides that will help in the perfect upbringing of the young generation. came Mawlana Jalaluddin Rumi, the great sheikh and poet, scholar of Sufism, founder of the Mawlavi sect, gained special value because of the common qualities of the mentioned ideals of perfection. Holy books and hadiths, theological-mystical and moral works created in the ancient East over the centuries served as a unique source for the birth of this rare work of Alloma. In the Eastern world, this work is considered a sacred source after the Holy Qur'an and hadiths, even about the work "Masnavii ma'navi" Mawlavi - Hast Qur'an dar zaboni Pahlavi", that is, "Masnavii ma' It is not for nothing that the full definition

of the confession that the "spiritual" is the Qur'an in the Pahlavi language has spread. Because the main principle of the work is to explain the essence of the Qur'anic verses and hadiths, combining them with mystical views, and the intended purpose was undoubtedly to contribute to the education of a perfect human being. Eastern thinkers have always been distinguished by their deep spiritual potential. They considered it as one of the important factors of moral maturity of a person, formation of his spiritual image, social and political development of society.¹

Maulana Rumi's moral-philosophical teaching is of great importance for philosophers to understand the world more deeply, to understand the secrets of the universe and human psyche, and to understand the essence of life's conflicts. The ideas put forward in Rumi's teaching encourage us to learn the inner law of perfection. Rumi's work is a new synthesis, harmony of the wisdom of Eastern science, the world of meanings, and at the same time, it is brought to a higher level and developed. That's why the advanced ideas put forward by the Sufism stirred up the people of thought and conquered the hearts. That is why the works of the philosopher-poet are still very relevant and important, keeping their miraculous power.

Today's cultural world honors a person who is in harmony with all humanity. Rumi's moral-philosophical position meets such requirements. That is why every young generation should enjoy Rumi's mystical ideas in order to be self-aware, to be able to control their emotions, to have their own thoughts, images, and views.

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